

Supplementary Material for Manuscript

A Signal Extraction Approach for Remote Heart Rate Variability Assessment Using Proxy Measure in a Driving Simulator

Corresponding Author, Đorđe D. Nešković, PhD Student and Junior Researcher Assistant

Affiliations: University of Belgrade - School of Electrical Engineering and Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade

E-mail: djordjeneskovic8@gmail.com

To ensure conciseness in the manuscript, detailed elaborations of selected methodological components are provided here as a supplementary material. The primary objective of this document is twofold: to thoroughly present the full methodological pipeline for the sake of reproducibility and to provide a comprehensive overview of results, enabling a clearer and more direct insight into the findings, discussion, and conclusions of the study. Each stage of the proposed remote PhotoPlethysmoGraphy (rPPG)-based pipeline is described in expanded form, covering facial region extraction and SuperPixel (SP) segmentation, signal preprocessing and quality assessment, peak enhancement strategies, Heart Rate Variability (HRV) parameter computation, as well as Inter-Beat-Interval (IBI)-based peak detection performance evaluation. The presentation follows the sequential structure of the corresponding subsections in the manuscript, allowing straightforward cross-referencing between the core manuscript and the additional methodological detail provided below.

Table of Contents

1. Method.....	2
1.1. Recording Procedure.....	2
1.2. Superpixel-based Selection of Regions of Interest	2
1.3. Phase Shift in rPPG After Application of Selected Methods.....	4
1.4. Detailed Approach to Estimation of the Signal-to-Noise Ratio.....	4
1.5. Peak Detection in Reference ECG	5
1.6. Detailed Presentation of Performed Statistical Analysis	5
2. Additional Results.....	7
3. Discussion.....	15
3.1. Additional Details on Region Selection and Parameter Enhancement	15
3.2. Additional Discussion on Signal Quality Assessment.....	15
3.3. Extended Discussion on Heart Rate Variability.....	16
3.4. Discussion on IBI Detection	18
3.5. Study Contributions	19
References.....	20

1. Method

The following subsections provide expanded descriptions of each methodological stage of the proposed pipeline, presented in the order in which they appear in the manuscript.

1.1. Recording Procedure

At the beginning of the measurement, participants complete a demographic questionnaire and adjust the seat, while researchers record the luminance. Illuminance is measured using a lux meter (<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.lux.light.meter&hl=en>, Accessed on May 16, 2026) application on a mobile phone (Samsung One UI version 7.0, Android version 15). The measured values during all recording sessions have a mean of 743.08 lx and a standard deviation of 10.31 lx. The ~30-minute measurement session includes three phases: 1) Baseline (BSL) — 15 minutes of seated relaxation, 2) familiarization — brief practice with controls and tasks in a simulated vehicle, and 3) Driving Simulation (DS) — highway driving under normal conditions for ~10 minutes, followed by ~2 minutes of a sudden dense fog. Participants are specifically instructed to drive safely and reach the destination. Facial videos are obtained during all three phases by an ELP High Resolution (HD) digital camera (Ailipu Technology Co., Ltd., Shenzhen, China) with resolution of 1920×1080 pixels at 30 frames per second (fps). As a reference, an ElectroCardioGraphy (ECG) signal is measured synchronously with the camera by using the BiosignalsPLUX wireless device (PLUX Biosignals, Lisbon, Portugal). The sampling frequency is set to 1000 Hz with gain of 1019. Timestamps from BiosignalsPLUX and camera recordings are used for synchronisation. Overall, 29 participants (17 males and 12 females) aged from 21 to 42 years (25.86 ± 5.75) completed a designated task in a simulated vehicle.

1.2. Superpixel-based Selection of Regions of Interest

The input video recordings are first segmented into non-overlapping sequences of 20 s [1], each of which are processed independently as a unit of analysis. For each 20 s segment, the Region of Interest (ROI) is defined through a hierarchical localization pipeline consisting of coarse head detection, refinement to the facial region, and subsequent decomposition into SP-based sub-regions from which pixel-level color information is sampled.

The first stage of the pipeline involves detecting the subject's head within the video frame. A Viola-Jones cascade object detector is applied to the first frame of the video sequence, configured to use a standard frontal face model [2-3]. Following initial detection, false positive bounding boxes are eliminated using a minimum size threshold of 150 pixels applied to both width and height. This value was empirically determined based on the recording setup: given the 1920×1080 resolution and the centered framing of participants, any genuine facial region is expected to occupy at least one fifth of the frame height, while spurious detections arising from background elements, such as wall outlets or other small objects, consistently produce bounding boxes well below this threshold.

Raw head bounding boxes typically encompass regions that include the forehead, hair, ears, and portions of the neck, all being areas that contribute little to physiological signal quality and may introduce noise due to hair movement or shadow variations [4]. To address this, the detected bounding box is geometrically refined to approximate the facial skin region more tightly. Symmetric horizontal insets of one-fifth of the box width are applied on each side, while vertical margins are trimmed asymmetrically: a smaller inset from the top and a larger reduction from the bottom, excluding the chin and neck. This asymmetric trimming reflects the anatomical structure of the face and centers the resulting ROI on the mid-face area, encompassing the cheeks, nose, and periorbital regions, which corresponds well to zones of high skin perfusion relevant for rPPG signal extraction.

Rather than treating the entire facial ROI as a single homogeneous signal source, the bounding box region is further decomposed into spatially compact sub-regions using SP segmentation [1]. The SP algorithm groups neighbouring pixels with similar color and texture properties into irregularly shaped, but spatially contiguous clusters, offering a compromise between pixel-level noise sensitivity and region-level spatial resolution [5]. In this work, a target counts of $N = 10$ and $N = 20$ SP are explored, selected on the basis of a preliminary pilot analysis as a practical compromise between computational complexity and spatial representativeness of the facial region, yielding coarser and finer spatial decompositions of the facial region, respectively. The polygon boundaries of each SP are computed from the label map of the first frame and used as the initial spatial definition of each ROI.

Figure A1: Visualization of the simulated results of CHROM, POS, and PCA approaches using sinusoidal RGB input components at 60 bpm with mutual phase shifts of $\pm 5^\circ$. The R and B channels are phase-shifted relative to the G channel. CHROM and POS outputs almost completely overlap, whereas the PCA-derived signal closely overlaps with the R channel.

A challenge in rPPG signal extraction is maintaining spatial correspondence of the ROIs across frames in the presence of subject head movement. Static ROI definitions degrade in the presence of even small translations or rotations, as regions may shift off the skin surface or straddle tissue boundaries. To address this, an optical flow-based tracking mechanism is incorporated [6]. Feature points are detected in the first frame within the facial bounding box using the minimum eigenvalue corner detector, and a Lucas-Kanade point [7] tracker is initialized with these points. For each subsequent frame, a similarity transformation, allowing translation, rotation, and uniform scaling, is estimated between the tracked feature point configurations. The resulting geometric transformation is then applied to the polygon vertex coordinates of each SP region, warping the boundaries to align with the facial geometry in the

current frame. If the number of successfully matched inlier correspondences fell below two (the theoretical minimum required for similarity transformation estimation), tracking is considered lost and processing is halted to prevent accumulation of severely misregistered data.

1.3. Phase Shift in rPPG After Application of Selected Methods

This chapter is presented in detail in the manuscript, here only additional figure is provided. Namely, Fig. A1 illustrates the simulated Red, Green, and Blue (RGB) input components and the corresponding extracted rPPG signals obtained using the Chrominance-based method (CHROM), Plane-Orthogonal-to-Skin (POS), and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) methods, generated from sinusoidal RGB signals at 60 beats per minute (bpm) with mutual phase shifts of $\pm 5^\circ$. Presented outputs from CHROM, POS, and PCA, clearly demonstrates the phase relationship between the input channels and the extracted signals: while the G channel serves as the reference, CHROM and POS produce signals that are visibly inverted relative to the input, with phase shifts of approximately -94° and -93° respectively. The PCA-derived signal, in contrast, closely tracks the green channel with a phase shift of only -5° . The exact phase values for all signals are reported in the manuscript.

1.4. Detailed Approach to Estimation of the Signal-to-Noise Ratio

The Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) of the extracted rPPG signal is estimated using power spectral analysis. The discrete Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) of each 20 s long non-overlapping signal segment is computed, and the Power Spectral Density (PSD) is obtained as the squared magnitude of the Fourier spectrum. Since the objective is to determine the dominant frequency with the highest possible precision, the PSD is estimated as the squared FFT magnitude rather than using Welch's method, which provides a more generalized spectral estimate. Three distinct SNR metrics are defined, each serving a specific purpose in the processing pipeline.

The first SNR metric, SNR narrow filt. ECG, is computed as the ratio of the PSD within a narrow band of ± 0.1 Hz centered at the dominant Heart Rate (HR) frequency obtained from the reference ECG signal to the remaining PSD outside this band, expressed in decibels (dB). This metric reflects how well the rPPG signal concentrates energy at the true cardiac frequency and is used for selecting the facial region with the highest signal quality. The use of a narrow band centered at the dominant cardiac frequency for SNR estimation follows the approach proposed in [8], which demonstrated that restricting the useful signal band to a tight window around the fundamental HR frequency provides a sensitive and discriminative measure of rPPG signal quality. In the present study, this narrow-band approach is applied in two variants: SNR narrow filt. ECG, where the center frequency is determined from the reference ECG signal, and SNR narrow filt. rPPG, where it is derived directly from the rPPG signal itself, enabling a comparison between externally referenced and self-referenced signal quality estimates.

The second SNR metric, SNR (0.7 Hz - 3 Hz), is defined over the full physiological HR band of 0.7 Hz - 3 Hz (corresponding to the range from 42 beats per minute (bpm) to 180 bpm), with the exception of a narrow notch of ± 0.1 Hz centered at 2 Hz, which is excluded from both the useful signal and noise calculations. This exclusion is applied to suppress a recurring non-physiological spectral artifact observed in several recordings. Since this particular artifact does not appear consistently across all recordings, it cannot be reliably classified as either noise or useful signal and therefore it is excluded from the SNR estimation entirely. The use of a broader physiological band for SNR computation follows the definitions adopted in [9, 10], which consider the full HR range as the relevant signal bandwidth rather than a narrow window around the dominant frequency. The noise power is defined as the remaining PSD outside the useful band, excluding the notched region. SNR (0.7 Hz - 3 Hz) is used as a segment rejection criterion, with any 20 s segment falling below a threshold of -17 dB discarded from further analysis, consistent with the discrimination threshold established in [10].

The third SNR metric, SNR narrow filt. rPPG, is computed similarly to SNR narrow filt. ECG, but instead of using the reference ECG frequency, the dominant frequency is determined directly from the rPPG signal PSD within the physiological HR band of 0.7 Hz – 3 Hz. Prior to identifying the dominant peak, the notch filter (± 0.1 Hz around 2 Hz) is applied to prevent the recurring artifact from being falsely identified as the dominant cardiac frequency. The dominant frequency is then taken as the frequency of the highest spectral peak in the filtered PSD. SNR narrow filt. rPPG is computed as the ratio of the spectral power within ± 0.1 Hz around this dominant rPPG frequency to the remaining out-of-band power, and is used for comparison with SNR narrow filt. ECG to assess the agreement between the rPPG-derived and ECG-derived dominant frequencies. SNR narrow filt. rPPG is also introduced as a self-referenced quality metric that can be applied in practical scenarios where a simultaneous reference ECG signal is unavailable, making it directly applicable to real-world contactless monitoring deployments.

1.5. Peak Detection in Reference ECG

As a reference, an ECG is used. Firstly, the ECG signal is segmented into non-overlapping 20 s sequences to match rPPG segmentation. R-peak detection is then performed using a modified version of the Pan–Tompkins algorithm adapted to account for high noise levels and the presence of pathological heartbeats observed under DS conditions [11]. The ECG signal is filtered with the bandpass filter (0.5 Hz–20 Hz) using the fourth-order Butterworth filter with zero-phase filtering to suppress baseline wander and high-frequency noise. This is followed by differentiation and squaring to enhance the QRS complexes. A zero-phase MA filter based on a Hann’s window with a width of 250 ms as a continuous sliding-window without overlapping is subsequently applied to obtain an envelope emphasizing candidate R-peak regions [12]. Then, instead of using a fixed global threshold, an adaptive threshold is employed. Candidate peaks are initially detected with a minimal threshold and a refractory period of 250 ms. Subsequently, the detection threshold is dynamically adjusted to half of the third quantile of the candidate peak amplitudes. This adaptive approach is important for preventing the exceptionally high R-peak amplitudes characteristic of certain pathological beats [13] from inflating the threshold. In this way, we avoid the suppression of normal beats following pathological beats, which could otherwise lead to missed detections. This adaptive approach improves robustness in highly noisy signals and in recordings containing irregular or pathological beats [13].

1.6. Detailed Presentation of Performed Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis is conducted for both the reference ECG-derived parameters and the rPPG-extracted parameters, and covers all combinations of the evaluated signal processing configurations: both 10 SP and 20 SP settings, two peak enhancement techniques (Lp norm and GL FOD), and four rPPG methods (Spatial Subspace Rotation (2SR), CHROM, POS, and PCA).

The normality of each data sample is assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. If both compared samples satisfy the normality criterion ($p > 0.05$), a two-sample Student's t-test is applied, while the effect size is quantified using Cohen's d . If either sample deviates significantly from normality ($p \leq 0.05$), the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test (also known as the Wilcoxon Rank-Sum test) is applied instead, and the effect size is quantified using Cliff's δ . In all cases, a significance threshold of $\alpha = 0.05$ is adopted, and differences are considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$. Effect size is additionally computed as a complementary measure of practical relevance, given that statistical significance alone does not preclude the possibility of trivially small differences being declared significant when sample sizes are sufficiently large [14]. Effect sizes are interpreted according to standard conventions: for Cohen's d , values below 0.2 are considered negligible, 0.2–0.5 small, 0.5–0.8 medium, and above 0.8 large. For Cliff's δ , the corresponding thresholds are 0.147, 0.33, and 0.474 [14].

The analysis is first applied to the reference ECG-derived parameters. Pulse rate (PR), Standard Deviation of Normal-to-Normal intervals (SDNN), and Root Mean Square of Successive Differences

(RMSSD) are each compared between the BSL and DS periods. This reference comparison provides the benchmark against the sensitivity of the rPPG-derived parameters. The same statistical procedure is then applied to the rPPG-extracted parameters across all evaluated method configurations. Specifically, the analysis is carried out for each of the four rPPG extraction methods (2SR, CHROM, PCA, and POS), under two region selection strategies (10 and 20 initial established regions) and two peak enhancement approaches (Lp norm and GL FOD). For each configuration, PR, SDNN, and RMSSD derived from the rPPG signal are compared between the BSL and DS periods. This systematic evaluation allows for a direct assessment of whether a given rPPG processing configuration is capable of capturing the physiologically meaningful cardiovascular changes induced by the DS task, in a manner consistent with the reference ECG-based findings.

2. Additional Results

This section provides a presentation of results obtained in the study, complementing the figures and tables that are not included in the manuscript. Specifically, Table A1 summarizes the most informative facial regions identified across all methods and configurations. Figs. A2, A3, and A4 present Bland–Altman plots, MAE, and RMSE for PR estimation corresponding to the 10 SP configuration, with Table A2 summarizing the numerical values for both 10 SP and 20 SP. MAE and RMSE for SDNN estimation (10 SP) are shown in Figs. A5 and A6, as well as summarized in Table A3, while Figs. A7 and A8 present the corresponding RMSSD results, summarized in Table A4. IBI peak detection performance under the Strict and Medium criteria are reported in Tables A6 - A7 (results under Relaxed criteria are presented in the manuscript in Table 1). SNR results for all three metrics are presented in Figs. A9, A10, and A11, and the full statistical analysis across all evaluated configurations is summarized in Table A5.

Table A1: Regions that proved to be the most useful for both initially determined SuperPixel (SP) regions, two peak enhancement approaches, and four remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) methods are presented. These regions are most related to the forehead and the cheeks in a slight favoring of the left side. Configuration of initially determined 20 SP regions: 1 – Left Forehead, 4 – Left Cheek, 5 – Left Cheech (sometimes region covered by glasses), 6 – Left Cheek, 7 – Left Cheek (sometimes nose), 8 – Forehead (Left of Right), 10 – Right Cheek (sometimes nose), 15 – right forehead; Initially determined 10 SP: 1 – Left Forehead, 2 – Left Cheek (sometimes region covered by glassed), 3 – Left Cheek, 4 – Left Cheek, 5 – Forehead (sometimes region covered by glasses), 6 – Left Cheek (sometimes nose), 7 – Forehead.

rPPG Methods	10 regions		20 regions	
	Lp norm	GL FOD	Lp norm	GL FOD
2SR	3, 1, 5, 2	1, 3, 2, 4	1, 4, 5, 15	1, 8, 5, 6
CHROM	1, 5, 3, 4	1, 3, 4, 5	1, 8, 2, 10	1, 4, 8, 6
POS	1, 7, 4, 3	4, 1, 3, 2	1, 10, 6, 8	1, 5, 6, 4
PCA	1, 3, 6, 4	1, 3, 4, 6	1, 4, 7, 8	4, 1, 5, 7

Figure A2: Bland-Altman plots for two peak enhancement approaches (Fractional Order Derivative - FOD and Lp norm) per each remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) method. Shown graphic corresponds to initially determined 10 SuperPixel (SP).

Figure A3: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between Heart Rate (HR) from the reference ElectroCardioGraphy (ECG) and extracted Pulse Rate (PR) for two peak enhancement approaches per each remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) method. Shown graphic corresponds to initially determined 10 SuperPixel (SP).

Figure A4: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between Heart Rate (HR) from the reference ElectroCardioGraphy (ECG) and extracted Pulse Rate (PR) for two peak enhancement approaches per each remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) method. Shown graphic corresponds to initially determined 10 SuperPixel (SP).

Table A2: Summarized results of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between Heart Rate (HR) from the reference ElectroCardioGraphy (ECG) and extracted Pulse Rate (PR) for two peak enhancement approaches per each remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) method. The shown table corresponds to both initially determined 20 SuperPixel (SP) and 10 SP.

rPPG Methods	MAE [bpm]							
	10 regions				20 regions			
	Lp norm		GL FOD		Lp norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	3.05±3.90	4.85±5.31	3.19±2.70	2.91±2.12	2.31±3.43	3.27±4.20	2.22 ±2.26	1.92±1.72
CHROM	3.07±3.56	4.45±4.04	3.65±3.26	3.67±2.97	2.33±3.53	3.25±3.50	2.63±2.76	2.42±2.38
POS	4.02±5.17	4.62±4.91	4.29±3.98	3.79±3.09	2.54±3.33	3.54±4.96	3.05±3.23	2.66±2.46
PCA	3.82±6.69	6.28±7.02	2.67±3.12	3.26±2.05	2.93±5.62	5.1±6.55	1.92±1.93	2.33±2.10
rPPG Methods	RMSE [bpm]							
	10 regions				20 regions			
	Lp norm		GL FOD		Lp norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	4.33±5.72	6.38±6.58	4.33±3.19	3.86±2.57	3.24±5.48	4.47±5.79	2.91±2.69	2.45±2.00
CHROM	4.33±5.30	6.00±5.60	4.75±3.69	4.77±3.42	3.16±5.30	4.45±5.19	3.33±3.24	3.01±2.58
POS	5.30±7.07	5.95±5.94	5.40±4.19	4.79±3.54	3.44±4.94	4.78±6.41	3.80±3.42	3.44±3.07
PCA	5.13±8.65	8.27±8.88	3.64±4.14	4.20±2.47	4.13±7.94	6.80±8.30	2.64±2.71	3.04±2.74

Figure A5: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between Standard Deviation of Normal-to-Normal Intervals (SDNN) from the reference ElectroCardioGraphy (ECG) and extracted SDNN for two peak enhancement approaches per each remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) method. Shown graphic corresponds to initially determined 10 SuperPixel (SP).

Figure A6: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between Standard Deviation of Normal-to-Normal Intervals (SDNN) from the reference ElectroCardioGraphy (ECG) and extracted SDNN for two peak enhancement approaches per each remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) method. Shown graphic corresponds to initially determined 10 SuperPixel (SP).

Figure A7: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between Root Mean Square of Successive Differences (RMSSD) from the reference ElectroCardioGraphy (ECG) and extracted RMSSD for two peak enhancement approaches per each remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) method. Shown graphic corresponds to initially determined 10 SuperPixel (SP).

Table A3: Summarized results of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between Standard Deviation of Normal-to-Normal Intervals (SDNN) from the reference ElectroCardioGraphy (ECG) and extracted SDNN for two peak enhancement approaches per each remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) method. The shown table corresponds to both initially determined 20 SuperPixel (SP) and 10 SP.

		MAE [s]							
rPPG Methods		10 regions				20 regions			
		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
		BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR		0.074±0.043	0.083±0.042	0.090±0.037	0.093±0.031	0.076±0.048	0.076±0.058	0.095±0.049	0.094±0.043
CHROM		0.082±0.050	0.081±0.038	0.093±0.033	0.094±0.027	0.081±0.048	0.072±0.055	0.092±0.038	0.094±0.034
POS		0.083±0.050	0.085±0.044	0.096±0.029	0.094±0.024	0.078±0.048	0.086±0.053	0.097±0.037	0.095±0.040
PCA		0.067±0.041	0.081±0.039	0.089±0.036	0.088±0.039	0.061±0.040	0.071±0.044	0.099±0.052	0.112±0.062
		RMSE [s]							
rPPG Methods		10 regions				20 regions			
		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
		BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR		0.102±0.054	0.097±0.055	0.114±0.040	0.104±0.0385	0.104±0.051	0.101±0.064	0.129±0.092	0.116±0.051
CHROM		0.107±0.055	0.110±0.070	0.113±0.037	0.116±0.042	0.109±0.051	0.105±0.066	0.115±0.037	0.115±0.036
POS		0.106±0.044	0.114±0.089	0.120±0.035	0.117±0.038	0.105±0.053	0.112±0.061	0.119±0.035	0.118±0.047
PCA		0.087±0.045	0.098±0.058	0.116±0.041	0.106±0.043	0.087±0.046	0.108±0.077	0.145±0.130	0.183±0.162

Table A4: Summarized results of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between Root Mean Square of Successive Differences (RMSSD) from the reference ElectroCardioGraphy (ECG) and extracted RMSSD for two peak enhancement approaches per each remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) method. The shown table corresponds to both initially determined 20 SuperPixel (SP) and 10 SP.

		MAE [s]							
rPPG Methods		10 regions				20 regions			
		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
		BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR		0.096±0.068	0.089±0.057	0.114±0.052	0.102±0.053	0.097±0.069	0.094±0.075	0.123±0.071	0.119±0.059
CHROM		0.099±0.071	0.107±0.103	0.116±0.051	0.116±0.049	0.102±0.069	0.095±0.064	0.116±0.047	0.118±0.047
POS		0.097±0.064	0.107±0.105	0.117±0.048	0.121±0.043	0.102±0.065	0.107±0.078	0.120±0.050	0.119±0.051
PCA		0.083±0.062	0.085±0.068	0.110±0.052	0.104±0.058	0.081±0.059	0.082±0.064	0.128±0.077	0.126±0.084
		RMSE [s]							
rPPG Methods		10 regions				20 regions			
		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
		BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR		0.133±0.077	0.123±0.075	0.144±0.056	0.130±0.063	0.1350±0.074	0.125±0.084	0.170±0.146	0.146±0.070
CHROM		0.137±0.076	0.141±0.107	0.1445±0.05 4	0.144±0.057	0.138±0.073	0.129±0.081	0.146±0.050	0.143±0.054
POS		0.134±0.068	0.142±0.133	0.149±0.053	0.148±0.048	0.138±0.071	0.142±0.100	0.149±0.051	0.145±0.051
PCA		0.119±0.079	0.118±0.084	0.143±0.067	0.129±0.067	0.122±0.065	0.111±0.082	0.183±0.173	0.179±0.175

Figure A9: Comparison of Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) values (useful part of Power Spectral Density (PSD) defined within a narrow band (± 0.1 Hz) centered at the reference Heart Rate (HR) frequency from the ElectroCardioGraphy (ECG)) across two peak enhancement approaches and four remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) methods. Shown graphic corresponds to initially determined 20 SuperPixel (SP).

Figure A10: Comparison of Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) values (useful part of the Power Spectral Density (PSD) defined within a narrow band (± 0.1 Hz) centered at the dominant frequency from the remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG)) across two peak enhancement approaches and four rPPG methods. Shown graphic corresponds to initially determined 20 SuperPixel (SP).

Table A5: Comparison of three different Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) values through two peak enhancement approaches and four remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) methods. The displayed values correspond to the initially determined 10 SuperPixel (SP) regions.

SNR narrow filt (ECG) [dB]				
rPPG Methods	10 regions			
	<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	-7.92±3.90	-9.75±4.01	-7.72±4.12	-9.88±4.21
CHROM	-11.12±4.34	-13.65±4.29	-11.19±4.37	-13.58±4.41
POS	-13.25±5.98	-16.50±5.26	-13.23±6.02	-16.47±5.36
PCA	-18.43±5.83	-19.19±5.00	-18.31±6.01	-19.41±5.07
SNR (0.7 Hz-3 Hz) [dB]				
rPPG Methods	10 regions			
	<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	-3.06±2.9	-4.30±3.08	-2.90±2.82	-4.39±3.39
CHROM	-6.51±3.33	-8.64±3.13	-6.54±3.23	-8.58±3.13
POS	-7.64±4.34	-10.80±3.47	-7.57±4.32	-10.71±3.54
PCA	-12.30±3.08	-12.83±2.75	-12.19±3.21	-12.86±2.81
SNR narrow filt (rPPG) [dB]				
rPPG Methods	10 regions			
	<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	-7.91±4.03	-9.65±4.07	-7.54±4.34	-9.27±4.49
CHROM	-10.84±5.24	-13.27±4.86	-10.86±5.10	-13.16±4.68
POS	-12.86±6.88	-15.76±6.82	-12.81±6.80	-15.83±5.79
PCA	-18.05±6.75	-18.13±7.08	-17.55±7.32	-17.80±7.05

Table A6: Inter-Beat Interval (IBI) metrics when the Strict criteria is defined (for more details, please see the manuscript). Both 10 SuperPixel (SP) and 20 SP regions are initially determined, two peak enhancement approaches and four remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) methods.

Precision								
rPPG Methods	10 regions				20 regions			
	<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	0.382	0.437	0.407	0.403	0.379	0.441	0.400	0.439
CHROM	0.389	0.436	0.404	0.408	0.388	0.450	0.391	0.414
POS	0.381	0.413	0.387	0.395	0.388	0.417	0.393	0.399
PCA	0.430	0.399	0.371	0.400	0.444	0.394	0.392	0.426
Inverted PCA	0.353	0.447	0.418	0.436	0.353	0.445	0.396	0.428
Recall								
rPPG Methods	10 regions				20 regions			
	<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	0.359	0.403	0.410	0.390	0.358	0.409	0.402	0.423
CHROM	0.370	0.405	0.410	0.399	0.369	0.421	0.397	0.406
POS	0.362	0.381	0.393	0.385	0.369	0.389	0.401	0.392
PCA	0.398	0.353	0.361	0.377	0.413	0.358	0.379	0.390
Inverted PCA	0.326	0.396	0.409	0.411	0.329	0.402	0.388	0.402
F1 score								
rPPG Methods	10 regions				20 regions			
	<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	0.370	0.419	0.408	0.396	0.369	0.425	0.401	0.431
CHROM	0.379	0.420	0.407	0.404	0.378	0.435	0.394	0.410
POS	0.371	0.396	0.390	0.390	0.378	0.402	0.397	0.395
PCA	0.413	0.375	0.366	0.388	0.428	0.375	0.385	0.407
Inverted PCA	0.339	0.420	0.414	0.423	0.341	0.422	0.392	0.415

Table A7: Inter-Beat Interval (IBI) metrics when it is considered according to the Medium definition of the IBI metrics. Both 10 SuperPixel (SP) and 20 SP regions are initially determined, two peak enhancement approaches and four remote PhotoPletismoGraphy (rPPG) methods.

Precision								
rPPG Methods	10 regions				20 regions			
	<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	0.507	0.590	0.532	0.571	0.501	0.589	0.524	0.596
CHROM	0.520	0.589	0.539	0.559	0.515	0.593	0.522	0.567
POS	0.509	0.567	0.516	0.544	0.523	0.571	0.526	0.546
PCA	0.577	0.545	0.522	0.532	0.580	0.542	0.534	0.543
Inverted PCA	0.477	0.587	0.529	0.581	0.477	0.583	0.519	0.575
Recall								
rPPG Methods	10 regions				20 regions			
	<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	0.477	0.543	0.536	0.553	0.473	0.547	0.526	0.574
CHROM	0.493	0.547	0.546	0.547	0.489	0.555	0.529	0.556
POS	0.484	0.522	0.524	0.530	0.499	0.533	0.537	0.536
PCA	0.534	0.482	0.509	0.501	0.540	0.493	0.515	0.497
Inverted PCA	0.441	0.521	0.517	0.547	0.444	0.528	0.508	0.539
F1 score								
rPPG Methods	10 regions				20 regions			
	<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD		<i>Lp</i> norm		GL FOD	
	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS	BSL	DS
2SR	0.492	0.566	0.534	0.562	0.487	0.567	0.525	0.584
CHROM	0.506	0.567	0.542	0.553	0.501	0.573	0.526	0.561
POS	0.496	0.544	0.520	0.537	0.511	0.551	0.531	0.541
PCA	0.555	0.512	0.515	0.516	0.559	0.516	0.524	0.519
Inverted PCA	0.458	0.552	0.523	0.564	0.460	0.554	0.513	0.556

3. Discussion

Additional discussion is presented within this chapter.

3.1. Additional Details on Region Selection and Parameter Enhancement

Our results suggest that the most informative facial regions are in line with the previous results and they are in majority of cases focused either solely on cheeks [15, 16] or on both cheeks and the forehead [17, 18]. Kwon et al. (2015) examined and identified 7 anatomical regions on a subjects' face for proper rPPG extraction and concluded that the forehead and cheeks are good candidates, while other parts are not, especially mouth and chin [17]. Across all methods and both SP configurations, cheek regions are selected more frequently than forehead regions. A consistent lateral preference for the left side of the face is observed across all configurations, with right-sided regions appearing only sporadically, primarily in the CHROM and POS configurations with 20 SP. We hypothesize that light influenced region selection as it is on the left side of the subject. No pronounced systematic differences between rPPG methods are observed in terms of region preference, suggesting that the spatial distribution of informative facial areas is largely method-independent and primarily driven by the intrinsic perfusion characteristics of the facial skin.

For the L_p norm, optimal values of p consistently cluster around 6 and 7, indicating a preference for more aggressive suppression of lower-amplitude components, which effectively sharpens the rPPG waveform peaks and improves the contrast between the cardiac-frequency component and background fluctuations. However, excessively high p values may disproportionately amplify the dominant peaks while suppressing smaller but physiologically valid beats, potentially introducing errors in IBI detection, especially when beat-to-beat amplitude variability is pronounced. In contrast, the GL FOD approach favours lower fractional orders, predominantly in the range of 1 to 1.4. This can be attributed to the fact that higher fractional orders progressively amplify high-frequency content [19], which in rPPG signals corresponds predominantly to noise rather than physiologically meaningful information. Orders between 1 and 1.4 therefore offer a favourable compromise between peak enhancement and noise suppression.

3.2. Additional Discussion on Signal Quality Assessment

As expected, SNR values under the broad-band definition (Fig. 6) are substantially higher than those obtained with narrow-band definition, since integrating over the full 0.7 Hz–3 Hz range distributes spectral energy across a much wider band, yielding a more conservative quality estimate. Of particular interest is the strong agreement between Figs. A9 and A10, which share the same narrow-band definition, but differ in reference frequency, ECG-derived HR versus the dominant rPPG spectral peak, respectively. Their close correspondence confirms that the extracted rPPG signal consistently identifies the true cardiac frequency as its dominant component. Across all three SNR definitions, the 2SR method consistently achieved the highest SNR values, while PCA yielded the lowest, a pattern that aligns with the greater segment rejection rate and higher estimation errors observed for PCA throughout the preceding analyses. The SNR (0.7–3 Hz) values are consistent with those reported in [10] (–6 to –17 dB), while the narrow-band values are lower than those in [8] (–2.90 dB to 9.20 dB for POS), which is expected given the different definitions: in [8], the useful signal is a narrow band around the dominant ECG frequency while noise encompasses only the remaining 0.7 Hz–4 Hz range, whereas in the present study the noise is defined as the entire out-of-band spectrum beyond the narrow useful window, resulting in a more conservative SNR estimate.

3.3. Extended Discussion on Heart Rate Variability

The Bland–Altman plots (Fig. 7) indicate generally good agreement between the rPPG-derived PR values and the reference HR obtained from ECG, with the majority of data points falling within acceptable limits of agreement (5 bpm) according to FDA-approved errors for clinical use [20] across all four rPPG methods and both peak enhancement approaches. While a modest increase in error magnitude is expected during the DS condition due to increased head movement, or physiological arousal, the observed error differences for PR assessment between BSL and DS are relatively small. This can be partially attributed to the SNR-based segment rejection mechanism employed during data cleaning, whereby segments falling below the -17 dB threshold defined by the broad-band SNR metric (SNR 0.7 Hz $- 3$ Hz) are discarded prior to analysis. To illustrate the scale of this rejection and its relation to the applied method, a sample recording comprises 69 segments, 45 during BSL and 24 during DS. Using the PCA method, 10 out of 45 BSL segments and 7 out of 24 DS segments are excluded based on the SNR criterion, in addition to one segment discarded due to face detection failure during DS. In contrast, the CHROM method applied to the same recording resulted in none rejection during BSL and only one during DS, highlighting the substantially different sensitivity of examined models to the SNR threshold.

The best achieved results, obtained with the 2SR method using 20 SP regions and GL FOD during the DS condition, with comparable values observed during BSL and also with the L_p norm, yield MAE of 1.92 ± 1.72 bpm and RMSE of 2.45 ± 2.00 bpm. Particularly relevant is the observation reported in [21], where PR estimation accuracy using POS degraded as the recording environment transitioned from a still condition (MAE of 1.10 bpm) to an interactive task setting (MAE of 3.08 bpm), highlighting the sensitivity of rPPG methods to motion complexity. The fact that the proposed framework achieves lower MAE even under the dynamic DS condition (Table A2) suggests that the combination of SP-based region selection, SNR-based excluding segments, and peak enhancement effectively mitigates motion-related signal degradation. A similar trend of substantially higher MAE and RMSE is evident when comparing against [22], where CHROM, POS, and ICA evaluated under natural movement conditions yielded MAE values of 6.86 bpm, 4.25 bpm, and 6.05 bpm, as well as RMSE values of 15.57 bpm, 12.06 bpm, and 13.30 bpm, respectively, all substantially higher than those obtained in the present study (Table A2, Fig. 8 in manuscript). The RMSE values shown in Table A2 follow a similar trend, with somewhat higher values reflecting the sensitivity of RMSE to occasional larger deviations, particularly under the DS condition and with the L_p norm approach in certain configurations. Notably, RMSE values obtained in the present study are also substantially lower than those reported for CHROM, POS, and ICA in [23] under still sitting conditions, where values of 2.39 bpm, 3.69 bpm, and 11.08 bpm were observed, respectively, further underscoring the benefit of the proposed region selection and enhancement strategies even relative to controlled laboratory benchmarks.

A consistent pattern observed across Table A2 is that results obtained with 20 initially defined SP regions generally outperform those using only 10 SP regions, both in terms of MAE and RMSE, across virtually all rPPG methods and peak enhancement approaches. This improvement can be attributed to the richer spatial sampling afforded by a larger number of initially assigned SP regions, which allows the subsequent region selection step to identify a more informative and representative subset of facial areas contributing to the rPPG signal. It is worth noting, however, that this performance gain comes at the cost of increased computational demand, the 20 SP configuration requires approximately twice the processing time compared to the 10 SP setup. For the best-performing 2SR method with GL FOD, transitioning from 10 to 20 SP regions reduced MAE from 3.19 ± 2.70 bpm to 2.22 ± 2.26 bpm during BSL ($\sim 30\%$) and from 2.91 ± 2.12 to 1.92 ± 1.72 bpm during DS ($\sim 34\%$), with corresponding RMSE reductions from 4.33 ± 3.19 bpm to 2.91 ± 2.69 bpm for BSL ($\sim 33\%$) and from 3.86 ± 2.57 bpm to 2.45 ± 2.00 bpm ($\sim 37\%$) for DS (Table A2). Across all methods and conditions, the transition from 10 SP to 20 SP regions consistently yields improvements in both MAE and RMSE, with the notable

exception of the PCA L_p norm configuration during DS, where a marginal increase in error is observed, consistent with PCA known sensitivity to noise.

The GL FOD peak enhancement approach tended to yield lower errors compared to the L_p norm in the 20 SP configuration, particularly during the DS condition (Table A2). For the 2SR method, GL FOD reduced MAE by $\sim 4\%$ during BSL (2.22 ± 2.26 bpm vs. 2.31 ± 3.43 bpm) and by $\sim 41\%$ during DS (1.92 ± 1.72 bpm vs. 3.27 ± 4.23 bpm), with analogous RMSE reductions of $\sim 10\%$ during BSL (2.91 ± 2.69 bpm vs. 3.24 ± 5.48 bpm) and $\sim 45\%$ during DS (2.45 ± 2.00 bpm vs. 4.47 ± 5.79 bpm). It is worth noting, however, that this advantage is not universal, for CHROM and POS, the L_p norm yields marginally lower MAE and RMSE values during BSL (e.g., CHROM: MAE 2.33 ± 3.53 bpm (L_p norm) vs. 2.63 ± 2.76 bpm (GL FOD); POS: MAE 2.54 ± 3.33 bpm (L_p norm) vs. 3.05 ± 3.23 (GL FOD) bpm), suggesting that under lower-noise baseline conditions, the L_p norm can provide comparable or slightly superior peak delineation. During DS, however, GL FOD consistently outperforms the L_p norm across all methods, suggesting that the GL FOD offers greater robustness under the more challenging recording conditions introduced by the DS. The PCA method, despite its higher segment rejection rate, produced competitive MAE and RMSE values in configurations where sufficient data are retained, which may reflect the fact that the SNR-based exclusion criterion effectively ensures that only high-quality segments contribute to its final performance metrics, making rPPG-based HRV estimation robust to the selection of techniques for rPPG calculation.

The success of rPPG-based HRV estimation is assessed through MAE and RMSE computed between the ECG-derived reference values and the extracted SDNN and RMSSD parameters, as summarized in Tables A3 and A4 for both SP configurations. The results reveal a considerably greater challenge in accurately reproducing SDNN and RMSSD parameters compared to PR estimation. This is expected given that HRV metrics are derived from IBI sequences, making them inherently more sensitive to peak detection errors, even small timing inaccuracies in individual beat localization can propagate into substantial deviations. Nevertheless, the obtained error magnitudes are broadly consistent with those reported in the literature, and notably competitive given the dynamic nature of the DS environment. As expected, SDNN estimation success is highly sensitive to recording conditions: literature values under still conditions range from 0.012 s [24] to 0.107 s [25], rising to 0.088 s – 0.189 s under motion or interactive task conditions [21, 26]. A similar pattern is evident for RMSSD, where errors reported under static conditions range from 0.016 s [24] to 0.093 s [21] (similar observed in [25] where range is from 0.073 ± 0.057 s to 0.108 ± 0.051 s), rising to 0.120 s during interactive tasks [21] and to ranges of 0.164 s – 0.219 s under frequent motion conditions [26]. The present study achieves the best-case SDNN MAE and RMSE values of 0.061 s and 0.087 s, as well as RMSSD MAE and RMSE of 0.081 s and 0.111 s, which are comparable to or better than literature values obtained in far less demanding, controlled environments.

Although differences between BSL and DS conditions are expected and reflected in the PR, the degradation in estimation accuracy, expressed as the increase in MAE and RMSE between the two conditions, remains modest across all methods and both SDNN and RMSSD parameters. As is the case there, this robustness is partly a consequence of the SNR-based preprocessing stage, which removes the most severely degraded segments before HRV computation, thereby preventing the worst-case signal artifacts from disproportionately inflating the error metrics under the more demanding DS condition. This stands in contrast to the notable error increases reported in [21, 26], when transitioning from static to motion or interactive conditions, where SDNN and RMSSD errors increased by up to $40\text{--}50\%$ relative to still recording baselines. The differences in SDNN and RMSSD estimation accuracy between BSL and DS conditions remain modest across all methods and configurations. The degradation in SDNN and RMSSD estimation accuracy from BSL to DS is consistently small across all methods and configurations. For SDNN, BSL-to-DS MAE differences remain below 10% in virtually all cases, for example, 2SR L_p norm (20 SP) shows no measurable change (0.076 s in both conditions, $\sim 0\%$), while POS GL FOD similarly remains stable at 0.095 s ($\sim 0\%$). For RMSSD, the pattern is analogous, with

2SR L_p norm (20 SP) showing a marginal improvement from 0.097 s (BSL) to 0.094 s (DS) ($\sim 3\%$), and CHROM GL FOD increasing by only 0.002 s ($\sim 2\%$). This stability represents a meaningful practical advantage of the proposed pipeline, attributable to the SNR-based segment rejection which effectively limits the influence of motion-induced signal degradation on HRV estimation accuracy.

The improvement when transitioning from 10 to 20 SP regions is generally modest compared to the gains observed for PR, ranging from approximately 5–15% in MAE and 3–12% in RMSE across most configurations. For instance, PCA with L_p norm during BSL shows a SDNN MAE reduction $\sim 9\%$, while CHROM with L_p norm during DS improves $\sim 11\%$. A similar trend is observed for RMSSD, with comparable improvement margins across methods and conditions. The comparatively smaller benefit of 20 SP regions for HRV parameters is consistent with the greater sensitivity of rPPG-based HRV metrics to individual peak localization errors, which are not fully mitigated by denser spatial sampling alone.

Inspecting the SDNN results (Fig. 9 in manuscript, Table A3), MAE values across most 20 SP configurations fall in the range of 0.06 s – 0.10 s, while RMSE values are generally between 0.086 s and 0.130 s. The RMSSD results (Fig. 10, Table A4) follow a similar pattern, with MAE ranging from approximately 0.081 s to 0.128 s and RMSE spanning 0.111 s to 0.183 s. These values compare favourably with literature benchmarks, for instance, SDNN and RMSSD error ranges of 0.075 s – 0.076 s and 0.096 s – 0.137 s reported for CHROM under frequent motion conditions [26], which is particularly noteworthy given the added complexity of the DS environment. Across both parameters, the 2SR and CHROM methods demonstrate slightly more stable behavior, while PCA with GL FOD and 20 SP stands out with elevated RMSE values reaching up to 0.183 s, consistent with its susceptibility to variance-dominated noise components. In contrast, the L_p norm configuration of PCA yields some of the lowest MAE values across all methods, underscoring the strong modulating effect of the peak enhancement strategy on PCA performance.

3.4. Discussion on IBI Detection

The IBI metrics are evaluated using Precision, Recall, and F1 score under three matching criteria of increasing tolerance, Strict, Medium, and Relaxed, as reported in Tables A6, and A7, and 1 in manuscript, respectively. As expected, performance metrics increase substantially as the matching criterion becomes more permissive. Under the Strict definition (Table A6), F1 scores range between 0.37 and 0.43 across all methods and configurations, improving to 0.49–0.58 under the Medium criterion (Table A7). The most pronounced improvement is observed under the Relaxed criterion (Table 1), where F1 scores rise to approximately 0.85–0.93 across virtually all configurations. These results are comparable with the literature, where IBI detection accuracy of 0.88 and 0.94 has been reported for CHROM and POS under resting [27], and an F1 score of 0.94 for a contact-based PPG vs ECG comparison using a PTT tolerance of 540 ms [28]. In our study, the applied tolerances are 350 ms and 250 ms (350 ms is selected based on a pilot analysis which confirmed that the mean delay between the extracted rPPG peak and the reference ECG R-peak is approximately 350 ms). This threshold is therefore more stringent than the 540 ms used in [28], meaning that peaks accepted as true positives in [28] would be rejected under our Medium criterion (delay of 350 ms).

Across all three criteria, the 2SR and CHROM methods tend to achieve slightly higher F1 scores compared to POS and PCA, consistent with the trends observed in the PR and HRV estimation results. PCA in particular shows greater variability across configurations, with performance more sensitive to the choice of peak enhancement approach and SP configuration. The differences in Precision, Recall, and F1 score between BSL and DS conditions are modest across all metrics and criteria, again suggesting that the SNR-based preprocessing effectively limits the influence of signal degradation during the DS on the final IBI detection outcome. No consistent advantage of one peak enhancement approach over the other is apparent in the IBI metrics under the Strict and Medium criteria (Tables A6 and A7). However, under the Relaxed criterion, the L_p norm demonstrates a slight, but consistent

advantage over GL FOD, for instance, for the 2SR method with 20 SP regions, Precision reaches 0.929 (BSL) and 0.926 (DS) with the L_p norm, compared to 0.863 (BSL) and 0.880 (DS) with GL FOD. This can be attributed to the temporal displacement of rPPG peaks introduced by the GL FOD, which depends on the local signal morphology and cannot be compensated by a fixed offset correction. As a consequence, the GL FOD-enhanced rPPG peak may occasionally shift outside the expected RR interval, causing two rPPG peaks to appear within a single inter-beat interval and reducing detection performance under the Relaxed criterion.

3.5. Study Contributions

This paper makes the following primary contributions:

1. The proposed pipeline incorporates a data-driven SP segmentation and region selection mechanism that identifies the most informative facial areas for rPPG extraction on a per-subject basis, reducing susceptibility to local noise and motion artifacts while improving signal quality relative to fixed region-of-interest approaches.
2. Four rPPG algorithms (2SR, CHROM, POS, and PCA) are systematically compared in terms of their ability to accurately reproduce PR, SDNN, and RMSSD relative to reference ECG measurements, evaluated separately during BSL and DS conditions, providing new insights into the relative strengths and limitations of each method under realistic, noisy DS research and offering concrete methodological guidance for researchers seeking reliable rPPG-based HRV parametrization in driving simulator settings.
3. Two novel peak enhancement approaches — the L_p norm and the GL FOD— are introduced and evaluated in combination with each rPPG method, alongside an SNR-based quality assessment framework for segment rejection, collectively addressing the key methodological challenges of robust IBI detection from facial video and assessing their respective contributions to the accuracy of all extracted rPPG-derived HRV parameters across both recording conditions.
4. Building upon our prior demonstration that PR/HR can be reliably estimated via rPPG in driving simulator environments [29], this study extends the application to virtual reality settings anticipating subject movements, introducing a fully contactless pipeline capable of operating under realistic and dynamic recording conditions characterized by head movement, illumination variability, and physiological arousal.

References

1. Bobbia, S., Luguern, D., Benezeth, Y., Nakamura, K., Gomez, R., & Dubois, J. (2018). Real-time temporal superpixels for unsupervised remote photoplethysmography. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops*, pp. 1341-1348.
2. Wang, Y.Q. An analysis of the Viola-Jones face detection algorithm. *Image Process. Line* 2014, 4, 128–148. <https://doi.org/10.5201/ipol.2014.104>
3. Viola, P.; Jones, M. Rapid object detection using a boosted cascade of simple features. In *Proceedings of the 2001 IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, CVPR 2001, Kauai, HI, USA, 8–14 December 2001; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2001; Volume 1, pp. 511–518. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2001.990517>
4. Lee, R. J., Sivakumar, S., & Lim, K. H. (2024). Review on remote heart rate measurements using photoplethysmography. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 83(15), 44699-44728. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-16794-9>
5. Wang, M., Liu, X., Gao, Y., Ma, X., & Soomro, N. Q. (2017). Superpixel segmentation: A benchmark. *Signal Processing: Image Communication*, 56, 28-39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.image.2017.04.007>
6. Sánchez, A., Ruiz, J. V., Moreno, A. B., Montemayor, A. S., Hernández, J., & Pantrigo, J. J. (2011). Differential optical flow applied to automatic facial expression recognition. *Neurocomputing*, 74(8), 1272-1282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2010.07.017>
7. Lucas, B. D., & Kanade, T. (1981, August). An iterative image registration technique with an application to stereo vision. In *IJCAI'81: 7th international joint conference on Artificial intelligence* (Vol. 2, pp. 674-679). <https://hal.science/hal-03697340v1>
8. Xi, L., Wu, X., Chen, W., Wang, J., & Zhao, C. (2022). Weighted combination and singular spectrum analysis based remote photoplethysmography pulse extraction in low-light environments. *Medical engineering & physics*, 105, 103822. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medengphy.2022.103822>
9. Benezeth, Y., Bobbia, S., Nakamura, K., Gomez, R., & Dubois, J. (2019). Probabilistic signal quality metric for reduced complexity unsupervised remote photoplethysmography. In *2019 13th International Symposium on Medical Information and Communication Technology (ISMICT)*, pp. 1-5, IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISMICT.2019.8744004>
10. Lin, Y. C., & Lin, Y. H. (2017). A study of color illumination effect on the SNR of rPPG signals. In *2017 39th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)*, pp. 4301-4304, IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2017.8037807>
11. Fariha, M. A. Z., Ikeura, R., Hayakawa, S., & Tsutsumi, S. (2020, June). Analysis of Pan-Tompkins algorithm performance with noisy ECG signals. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1532, No. 1, p. 012022). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1532/1/012022>
12. De Haan, G., & Jeanne, V. (2013). Robust pulse rate from chrominance-based rPPG. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 60(10), 2878-2886. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2013.2266196>
13. Mager, J. (2015). Automatic threshold selection of the peaks over threshold method. *Technical University of Munich Department of Mathematics*, 114, Master Thesis, Available online: <https://mediatum.ub.tum.de/doc/1254349/document.pdf>, Accessed on February 26, 2026.
14. Hess, M.R.; Kromrey, J.D. Robust confidence intervals for effect sizes: A comparative study of Cohen's d and Cliff's delta under non-normality and heterogeneous variances. In *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the American Educational Research Association*, San Diego, CA, USA, 12–16 April 2004; Volume 1.
15. Speth, J.; Vance, N.; Flynn, P.; Bowyer, K.; Czajka, A. Unifying frame rate and temporal dilations for improved remote pulse detection. *Comput. Vis. Image Underst.* 2021, 210, 103246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cviu.2021.103246>.
16. Caroppo, A., Manni, A., Rescio, G., Siciliano, P., & Leone, A. (2024). Vital signs estimation in elderly using camera-based photoplethysmography. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 83(24), 65363-65386. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-18053-3>.
17. Kwon, S.; Kim, H.; Park, K.S. Validation of heart rate extraction using video imaging on a built-in camera system of a smartphone. In *Proceedings of the 2012 Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*, San Diego, CA, USA, 28 August–1 September 2012; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2012; pp. 2174–2177. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2012.6346392>.
18. Nagar, S., Hasegawa-Johnson, M., Beiser, D. G., & Ahuja, N. (2024). R21-rPPG: A robust region of interest selection method for remote photoplethysmography to extract heart rate. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.15851*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.15851>.
19. Wang, Q., Ma, J., Yu, S., & Tan, L. (2020). Noise detection and image denoising based on fractional calculus. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 131, 109463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2019.109463>.
20. Lee, C.; Lee, C.; Fernando, C.; Chow, C.M. Comparison of Apple watch vs KardiaMobile: A tale of two devices. *CJC Open* 2022, 4, 939–945. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjco.2022.07.011>.
21. Talukdar, D., De Deus, L. F., & Sehgal, N. (2023). The Evaluation of Remote Monitoring Technology Across Participants With Different Skin Tones. *Cureus*, 15(9). <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.45075>.

22. Wang, K., Wei, Y., Tang, J., Wang, Y., Li, Z., Tong, M., ... & Zhao, Z. (2024, December). Camera-based hrv prediction for remote learning environments. In *2024 IEEE Smart World Congress (SWC)* (pp. 1165-1173). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SWC62898.2024.00185>.
23. Bobbia, S.; Macwan, R.; Benezeth, Y.; Mansouri, A.; Dubois, J. Unsupervised skin tissue segmentation for remote photoplethysmography. *Pattern Recognition Letter* 2019, 124, 82–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2017.10.017>.
24. Finžgar, M., & Podržaj, P. (2020). Feasibility of assessing ultra-short-term pulse rate variability from video recordings. *PeerJ*, 8, e8342. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.8342>.
25. Odinaev, I., Wong, K. L., Chin, J. W., Goyal, R., Chan, T. T., & So, R. H. (2023). Robust heart rate variability measurement from facial videos. *Bioengineering*, 10(7), 851. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bioengineering10070851>.
26. Huang, R. Y., & Dung, L. R. (2016). Measurement of heart rate variability using off-the-shelf smart phones. *Biomedical Engineering Online*, 15(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12938-016-0127-8>.
27. Sun, Z., Junttila, J., Tulppo, M., Seppänen, T., & Li, X. (2022). Non-contact atrial fibrillation detection from face videos by learning systolic peaks. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 26(9), 4587-4598. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JBHI.2022.3193117>.
28. Kotzen, K., Charlton, P. H., Landesberg, A., & Behar, J. A. (2021, September). Benchmarking photoplethysmography peak detection algorithms using the electrocardiogram signal as a reference. In *2021 Computing in Cardiology (CinC)* (Vol. 48, pp. 1-4). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.23919/CinC53138.2021.9662889>.
29. Nešković, Đ. D., Stojmenova Pečečnik, K., Sodnik, J., & Miljković, N. (2025). Contactless pulse rate assessment: Results and insights for application in driving simulators. *Applied Sciences*, 15(17), 9512. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app15179512>.